

Emergency point-of-care ultrasound use in Africa

PID 1858

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Codebook ▾

Data Dictionary Codebook

18/10/2021 10:26

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#	Variable / Field Name	Field Label <i>Field Note</i>	Field Attributes (Field Type, Validation, Choices, Calculations, etc.)												
Instrument: Emergency point-of-care ultrasound in Africa (emergency_pointofcare_ultrasound_in_africa) Enabled as survey ^ Collapse															
1	participant_id	Participant ID	text												
2	consent	Section Header: <i>Consent</i> I understand that my participation in this study is entirely voluntary and that there are no monetary benefits for participation.	radio <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>I agree to participate</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>I don't want to participate</td></tr> </table> Stop actions on 2	1	I agree to participate	2	I don't want to participate								
1	I agree to participate														
2	I don't want to participate														
3	age	Section Header: <i>Demographic details</i> Please indicate your age in years	text, Required												
4	gender	Please indicate your gender	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Male</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Female</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Male	2	Female	3	Other						
1	Male														
2	Female														
3	Other														
5	gender_other Show the field ONLY if: [gender] = '3'	Please describe your gender	text, Required												
6	job	Which healthcare provider group do you belong to?	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Pre-hospital</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Nursing</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Doctors</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Pre-hospital	2	Nursing	3	Doctors	4	Other				
1	Pre-hospital														
2	Nursing														
3	Doctors														
4	Other														
7	job_other Show the field ONLY if: [job] = '4'	Please describe the healthcare group you belong to	text												
8	work	On average, what take up the biggest part of your work?	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Mostly clinical</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Mostly educational</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Mostly research</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Mostly administration</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Mostly clinical	2	Mostly educational	3	Mostly research	4	Mostly administration	5	Other		
1	Mostly clinical														
2	Mostly educational														
3	Mostly research														
4	Mostly administration														
5	Other														
9	work_other Show the field ONLY if: [work] = '5'	Please describe what take up the biggest part of your work	text, Required												
10	qualification	Please indicate your highest qualification	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Diploma or equivalent</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Bachelor's degree or equivalent</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Honour's degree or equivalent</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Master's degree or equivalent</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Doctoral degree or equivalent</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Diploma or equivalent	2	Bachelor's degree or equivalent	3	Honour's degree or equivalent	4	Master's degree or equivalent	5	Doctoral degree or equivalent	6	Other
1	Diploma or equivalent														
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3	Honour's degree or equivalent														
4	Master's degree or equivalent														
5	Doctoral degree or equivalent														
6	Other														
11	qualification_other Show the field ONLY if: [qualification] = '6'	Please describe your highest qualification	text, Required												

12	continent_primary	On which continent did you obtain your primary medical qualification?	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Africa</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Asia</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Australia</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Europe</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>North America</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>South America</td></tr> </table>	1	Africa	2	Asia	3	Australia	4	Europe	5	North America	6	South America						
1	Africa																				
2	Asia																				
3	Australia																				
4	Europe																				
5	North America																				
6	South America																				
13	primary_qual	In which year did you obtain your primary qualification?	text (integer), Required																		
14	specialise Show the field ONLY if: [job] = '3'	Have you specialized beyond your primary medical degree?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No														
1	Yes																				
0	No																				
15	spec Show the field ONLY if: [specialise] = '1'	Please indicate which specialty you are qualified in	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>spec__1</td><td>Emergency Medicine</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>spec__2</td><td>Anesthesiology</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>spec__3</td><td>Critical care</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>spec__4</td><td>Internal medicine</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>spec__5</td><td>Radiology</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>spec__6</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	spec__1	Emergency Medicine	2	spec__2	Anesthesiology	3	spec__3	Critical care	4	spec__4	Internal medicine	5	spec__5	Radiology	6	spec__6	Other
1	spec__1	Emergency Medicine																			
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3	spec__3	Critical care																			
4	spec__4	Internal medicine																			
5	spec__5	Radiology																			
6	spec__6	Other																			
16	spec_other Show the field ONLY if: [spec(6)] = '1'	Please describe which specialty you are working in	text, Required																		
17	continent_special Show the field ONLY if: [specialise] = '1'	On which continent did you obtain your specialist medical qualification?	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Africa</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Asia</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Australia</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Europe</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>North America</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>South America</td></tr> </table>	1	Africa	2	Asia	3	Australia	4	Europe	5	North America	6	South America						
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2	Asia																				
3	Australia																				
4	Europe																				
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6	South America																				
18	special_qual Show the field ONLY if: [specialise] = '1'	In which year did you obtain your specialist medical qualification?	text (integer), Required																		
19	continent_work	On which continent did you work most of the time over the last five years?	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Africa</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Asia</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Australia</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Europe</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>North America</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>South America</td></tr> </table>	1	Africa	2	Asia	3	Australia	4	Europe	5	North America	6	South America						
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6	South America																				

20 african_country

Show the field ONLY if:
[continent_work] = '1'Please indicate in which African country have you work
most of the time over the last five years?

dropdown (autocomplete)

1	Algeria
2	Angola
3	Benin
4	Botswana
5	Burkina Faso
6	Burundi
7	Cameroon
8	Cape Verde
9	Central African Republic
10	Chad
11	Comoros
12	Democratic Republic of the Congo
13	Djibouti
14	Egypt
15	Equatorial Guinea
16	Eswatini (Swaziland)
17	Eritrea
18	Ethiopia
19	Gabon
20	Gambia
21	Ghana
22	Guinea
23	Guinea-Bissau
24	Ivory Coast
25	Kenya
26	Lesotho
27	Liberia
28	Libya
29	Madagascar
30	Malawi
31	Mali
32	Mauritania
33	Mauritius
34	Morocco
35	Mozambique
36	Namibia
37	Niger
38	Nigeria
39	Republic of the Congo
40	Rwanda
41	Sao Tome and Principe
42	Senegal
43	Seychelles
44	Sierra Leone
45	Somalia
46	South Africa
47	South Sudan
48	Sudan
49	Tanzania
50	Togo
51	Tunisia
52	Uganda
53	Zambia
54	Zimbabwe

21	epocus_use	Section Header: <i>Emergency Point-of-Care Ultrasound (ePoCUS)</i> Do you use ePoCUS?	yesno, Required 1 Yes 0 No
22	reasons_not Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '0'	Please indicate all potential reasons for not using ePoCUS	checkbox, Required 1 reasons_not__1 I haven't been adequately trained 2 reasons_not__2 I don't have access to supervision or feedback 3 reasons_not__3 I have problems related to ultrasound machines or related consumables 4 reasons_not__4 I have easier alternative ultrasound access where I work 5 reasons_not__5 In-hospital specialties don't allow me to do ePoCUS 6 reasons_not__6 Other
23	reasons_not_other Show the field ONLY if: [reasons_not(6)] = '1' and [epocus_use] = '0'	Please give additional reasons for not using ePoCUS	text, Required
24	equipment Show the field ONLY if: [reasons_not(3)] = '1'	Please indicate all your problems related to ultrasound machines or related consumables	checkbox, Required 1 equipment__1 Lack of easy access to ultrasound machines 2 equipment__2 Regular failure of machines 3 equipment__3 Lack of ultrasound-related consumables (e.g. gel) 4 equipment__4 Lack of specific ultrasound probes 5 equipment__5 Other
25	equipment_other Show the field ONLY if: [equipment(5)] = '1'	Please describe other problems related to ultrasound machines or related consumables	text, Required
26	training Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	What training have you had in ePoCUS? (Select all options that apply)	checkbox, Required 1 training__1 Attended on-line courses only 2 training__2 Attended courses with hands-on training 3 training__3 Supervised hands-on training 4 training__4 I taught myself 5 training__5 Other
27	other_training Show the field ONLY if: [training(5)] = '1'	Please describe your other ePOCUS-related training	text Custom alignment: RH
28	accredited Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	Have you been accredited* to perform ePoCUS?(* i.e. you've been tested and evaluated by an outside person, committee, or organisation to ensure you meet the required standards)	yesno, Required 1 Yes 0 No Custom alignment: RH
29	who_accredited Show the field ONLY if: [accredited] = '1'	Please list the committee(s) or organization(s) who provided the accreditation (e.g. Emergency Medicine Society of South Africa)	text, Required Custom alignment: RH
30	perceived_skill Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	Please indicate your overall self-perceived level of ePoCUS skills	slider (number), Required Slider labels: No skill, Average, Worldclass master Custom alignment: RH
31	stealth Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	How often do you use ePoCUS to make clinical decisions without receiving hands-on training for the specific module application (e.g ultrasound-guided central venous access)?	slider (number), Required Slider labels: Never, Sometimes, All the time Custom alignment: RH

32	trauma Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	Section Header: <i>Please indicate which ePoCUS modules you use as well as the frequency</i> Trauma Ultrasound (Extended Focused Assessment with Sonography for Trauma (E-FAST))	radio (Matrix), Required 1 Daily 2 Weekly 3 Monthly 4 Less than once a month 5 Never
33	cardiac Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	Focused Cardiac Assessment	radio (Matrix), Required 1 Daily 2 Weekly 3 Monthly 4 Less than once a month 5 Never
34	obs1 Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	Obstetric ultrasound 1st semester (e.g. confirming intra-uterine pregnancy)	radio (Matrix), Required 1 Daily 2 Weekly 3 Monthly 4 Less than once a month 5 Never
35	obs2 Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	Obstetric ultrasound 2nd semester (e.g. assessing fetal viability, growth, multiple pregnancy, placenta location))	radio (Matrix), Required 1 Daily 2 Weekly 3 Monthly 4 Less than once a month 5 Never
36	obs3 Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	Obstetric ultrasound 3rd semester (e.g. assessing fetal viability, growth, multiple pregnancy, placenta location)	radio (Matrix), Required 1 Daily 2 Weekly 3 Monthly 4 Less than once a month 5 Never
37	thoracic Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	Thoracic assessment (including lung ultrasound)	radio (Matrix), Required 1 Daily 2 Weekly 3 Monthly 4 Less than once a month 5 Never
38	biliary Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	Liver and biliary assessment	radio (Matrix), Required 1 Daily 2 Weekly 3 Monthly 4 Less than once a month 5 Never
39	urinary Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	Urinary tract assessment (including bladder)	radio (Matrix), Required 1 Daily 2 Weekly 3 Monthly 4 Less than once a month 5 Never
40	dvt Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	Deep venous thrombosis (DVT) assessment	radio (Matrix), Required 1 Daily 2 Weekly 3 Monthly 4 Less than once a month 5 Never

41	soft_tissue Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	Soft-tissue/musculoskeletal/fracture assessment	radio (Matrix), Required 1 Daily 2 Weekly 3 Monthly 4 Less than once a month 5 Never
42	ocular Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	Ocular assessment	radio (Matrix), Required 1 Daily 2 Weekly 3 Monthly 4 Less than once a month 5 Never
43	shock Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	Shock assessment (e.g RUSH, EGLS etc)	radio (Matrix), Required 1 Daily 2 Weekly 3 Monthly 4 Less than once a month 5 Never
44	fash Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	Focused assessment with sonography for HIV-associated tuberculosis (FASH)	radio (Matrix), Required 1 Daily 2 Weekly 3 Monthly 4 Less than once a month 5 Never
45	abue Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	Abdominal assessment for undifferentiated abdominal pain or distention (ABUE)	radio (Matrix), Required 1 Daily 2 Weekly 3 Monthly 4 Less than once a month 5 Never
46	git Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	Gastro-intestinal tract assessment (e.g. appendicitis)	radio (Matrix), Required 1 Daily 2 Weekly 3 Monthly 4 Less than once a month 5 Never
47	reg Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	Procedural: Regional anesthesia	radio (Matrix), Required 1 Daily 2 Weekly 3 Monthly 4 Less than once a month 5 Never
48	tho Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	Procedural: Thoracentesis	radio (Matrix), Required 1 Daily 2 Weekly 3 Monthly 4 Less than once a month 5 Never
49	para Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	Procedural: Paracentesis	radio (Matrix), Required 1 Daily 2 Weekly 3 Monthly 4 Less than once a month 5 Never

50	peri Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	Procedural: Pericardiocentesis	radio (Matrix), Required 1 Daily 2 Weekly 3 Monthly 4 Less than once a month 5 Never
51	p_vasc Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	Procedural: Peripheral vascular access	radio (Matrix), Required 1 Daily 2 Weekly 3 Monthly 4 Less than once a month 5 Never
52	c_vasc Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	Procedural: Central vascular access	radio (Matrix), Required 1 Daily 2 Weekly 3 Monthly 4 Less than once a month 5 Never
53	other Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	Other	radio (Matrix), Required 1 Daily 2 Weekly 3 Monthly 4 Less than once a month 5 Never
54	other_describe Show the field ONLY if: [other] = '1' or [other] = '2' or [other] = '3' or [other] = '4'	Please list the other ePOCUS modules you use	text, Required Custom alignment: RH
55	covid_use Show the field ONLY if: [epocus_use] = '1'	Section Header: <i>ePOCUS use in COVID-19</i> How often have you used ePoCUS to assess patients suspected of having COVID-19?	radio, Required 1 Very often 2 Often 3 Occasionally 4 Seldom 5 Once or twice 6 Never
56	covid_why Show the field ONLY if: [covid_use] = '1' or [covid_use] = '2' or [covid_use] = '3' or [co vid_use] = '4' or [covid_use] = ' 5'	What did you use ePoCUS for in patients suspected of having COVID-19?	checkbox, Required 1 covid_why__1 Disposition 2 covid_why__2 Oxygen therapy adjustments 3 covid_why__3 Diagnostic 4 covid_why__4 Prognostic 5 covid_why__5 Other
57	covid_why_other Show the field ONLY if: [covid_why(5)] = '1'	Please describe other indications of ePOCUS you used for in patients suspected of having COVID-19?	text, Required Custom alignment: RH
58	covid_manage Show the field ONLY if: [covid_use] = '1' or [covid_use] = '2' or [covid_use] = '3' or [co vid_use] = '4' or [covid_use] = ' 5'	How often did ePoCUS change the management of your patients suspected of having COVID-19?	radio, Required 1 Very often 2 Often 3 Occasionally 4 Seldom 5 Once or twice 6 Never

	<p>59 covid_no</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [covid_use] = '6'</p>	<p>Please indicate why you have not use ePoCUS to assess patients suspected of having COVID-19? Can select more than one reason.</p>	<p>checkbox, Required</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="1015 129 1038 163">1</td> <td data-bbox="1038 129 1166 163">covid_no__1</td> <td data-bbox="1166 129 1474 185">The sensitivity of ePoCUS to rule out COVID-19 is too low</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1015 185 1038 219">2</td> <td data-bbox="1038 185 1166 219">covid_no__2</td> <td data-bbox="1166 185 1474 241">The specificity of ePoCUS to rule in COVID-19 is too low</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1015 241 1038 275">3</td> <td data-bbox="1038 241 1166 275">covid_no__3</td> <td data-bbox="1166 241 1474 331">ePoCUS does not add prognostic value to potential COVID-19 patients</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1015 331 1038 365">4</td> <td data-bbox="1038 331 1166 365">covid_no__4</td> <td data-bbox="1166 331 1474 421">We did not had an ultrasound machine to use in fear of contamination</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1015 421 1038 454">5</td> <td data-bbox="1038 421 1166 454">covid_no__5</td> <td data-bbox="1166 421 1474 454">Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	covid_no__1	The sensitivity of ePoCUS to rule out COVID-19 is too low	2	covid_no__2	The specificity of ePoCUS to rule in COVID-19 is too low	3	covid_no__3	ePoCUS does not add prognostic value to potential COVID-19 patients	4	covid_no__4	We did not had an ultrasound machine to use in fear of contamination	5	covid_no__5	Other
1	covid_no__1	The sensitivity of ePoCUS to rule out COVID-19 is too low																
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5	covid_no__5	Other																
	<p>60 covid_no_other</p> <p>Show the field ONLY if: [covid_no(5)] = '1'</p>	<p>Please describe your reasons for not using ePoCUS to assess patients suspected of having COVID-19?</p>	<p>text, Required</p> <p>Custom alignment: RH</p>															
	<p>61 emergency_pointofcare_ultrasound_in_africa_complete</p>	<p>Section Header: <i>Form Status</i></p> <p>Complete?</p>	<p>dropdown</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="1015 611 1038 645">0</td> <td data-bbox="1038 611 1150 645">Incomplete</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1015 645 1038 678">1</td> <td data-bbox="1038 645 1150 678">Unverified</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1015 678 1038 712">2</td> <td data-bbox="1038 678 1150 712">Complete</td> </tr> </table>	0	Incomplete	1	Unverified	2	Complete									
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